

Research Article

A Current View on Nursing Education and Research of Undergraduate and Postgraduate of Nursing Students

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Abstract:

Background: Nursing education and research is very important essential in nursing field in India. It is a very high demand in developed and developing countries. It generates many eminent nurses, nursing educators, managers, and nursing executives. In this present article, I have discussed the current status, issues of under and postgraduate nursing education, research, and its challenges.

Materials and Methods: Nursing education gives to a student to become a good professional in their future and as well as gives to them good knowledge about clinical research and its applications. Implementing advanced skills in their subject and as well as in the clinical skills through simulation techniques.

Results: Changing the under and postgraduate nursing education curriculum as per the modern world and introducing the advanced version/techniques of teaching and learning methods in all the sections of nursing education programs. Then only we must improve the standard of nursing education and research in India.

Conclusion: I have concluded that the nursing students to make a good knowledge in theory, research, and clinical skills by improving nursing education curriculum and by intensive training to them. By encourage the nursing students to do some clinical related studies/research after getting the research committee and ethical committee approval from their respective institutions.

Keywords: nursing, teaching, research, undergraduate, postgraduate, simulation.

1. Introduction

Nursing education means it contains two major parts like theoretical and practical training to them to prepare them to do their duties as nursing care professionals. In India, nursing professionals 30% of the national healthcare workforce. [1] the nursing education curriculum is governed by Indian Nursing Council (INC). INC is an autonomous body under Government of India and Ministry of Health & Family Welfare. [2] Nursing education is producing well-qualified, good professionals and give a best quality health care based on evidence and scientific based. Nursing related professionals are need required skills to get required knowledge, information, and skills by update their knowledge through the resources in their hospitals/institutions/organizations. Then, only they will have to give a high-quality health care to their patients. [3, 4] To improve an under and postgraduate nursing

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student's critical thinking and decision making on the spot skills by implementing an evidence-based education curriculum/education [5].

Nursing education and Simulation

Nursing education means that education with theory and clinical skills through simulation lab. Evidence-based practice (EBP) and teaching are exclusively needs in the undergraduate and postgraduate nursing teaching and learning but it has some difference in it. [7] In India, most of the nursing colleges simulation lab with mannequins (manual operating dummies) only. Simulation is giving a lively experience in various aspects. [8] This will improve the nursing students' knowledge, technical and interactive habits/skills and develop them in different thinking and quick response and to become a skilled professional in it. [9] In some nursing colleges inadequate simulation skill training facilities, and its utilization by the nursing students. [10] Simulation and other theoretical lessons, techniques have made a nursing student to a good, efficient, well trained, and successful healthcare professionals. [11–12] Simulation covers the expectations in the current context of nursing education for theory and practice. [13] Nowadays, the simulation lab skill is very much essential to work in abroad countries like USA, UK and other developed countries. Any nursing professionals are needed to get job in abroad countries then they need a certificate in simulation software and procedures. In India, nursing education geographically imbalanced due to various problems which constitute clinical skills and in knowledge in theory also. [14–15] Therefore, there is need to form a well-equipped and with well experienced simulation technique educator in nursing colleges to teach to the nursing students which will improve the quality of care and safety of the patients in the respective clinical departments [16 – 18].

Nursing Research

Nursing research (NR) [19] has a tremendous influence on current and future professional nursing practice, that's why it an important component of the nursing educational process. Undergraduate nursing students who are having the opportunity to do their studies and funding from the National Institute of Nursing Research, India. NR is critical to the nursing profession, and it is necessary for continuous advancements in nursing that will promote an optimal nursing profession/nursing care nursing research. Nowadays in India in all nursing colleges a separate Nursing Research Committee (NRC) is there to do research in nursing field. This will increase the quality and improve the development of nursing science and its research in clinical nurses. [20] Integrative review method has allowed for diverse primary research methods, and it becomes a greater part of EBP. [21] Nowadays, conducting number of health research is in high. To improve the health research/studies in nursing by the nursing faculties with proper knowledge and evidence-based knowledge is required. Research related to nursing areas are increased in developed countries with nursing faculties, health care workers and in management are playing in greater role. By this they can accommodate or combined with their co-worker in a good way/manner. The number of nursing research would be increased with the help of Ph.D in Nursing program automatically will increase nursing research in India.

Facing problems by nursing students

Both UG and PG nursing students are prepared their research proposals in their areas/specialties with their principal investigator/professor, submitted and presented in front of nursing college research committee and then sent the same to the medical college research committee also. Most of the nursing colleges are established/situated under the medical college campus itself. So, medical college research committee is only governing the nursing students and faculties research proposals. At that time, some of the research proposals be rejected due to some ethical issues. So, the nursing students are restricted to do their research works mostly as retrospective/secondary data-based studies only. This would be rectified by fixing a co-guide from the clinical side and to allow the nursing students to do prospective studies in their academic year. These types of problems are facing by the nursing students and faculties. Nursing research has faced some more difficulties after COVID-19. [22] The clinical staffs including nurses and health professionals have played a main role in clinical trials related to COVID-19, carrying, and supporting the COVID-19 patients in the teaching medical hospitals and hospitals [23].

2. Conclusion

Nursing profession is mainly to help assist to the physicians in medical field. Nursing professionals are working in a shift-based work only in worldwide. Many nurses are working with full of responsibilities in various areas departments. More number of nurses are need to the modern world. For this greater number of eminent nursing educators professors are needed worldwide. Nursing faculties are also improving their knowledge, skills and in research through various existing resources. To make the nursing students as good knowledge in theory, research, and clinical skills by improving the nursing education curriculum and by intensive training to them. By encourage the nursing students to do some clinical related studies research after getting the research committee and ethical committee approval from their respective hospital universities institutions organization. Identify the good, dedicated, and keen knowledge in clinical area nurses and to give them some considerable incentives or a proper theoretical and recent clinical trainings to the nursing professionals through some workshop/staff development training once/twice in a year with free of cost. Then only, we will strengthen both undergraduate and postgraduate nursing students' knowledge in nursing education and research in a systematic way.

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